

An observational trial to find the rate of azolla multiplication in February-April 1981 examined 4 levels of azolla (200, 400, 800, 1600 g/m²) and 2 levels of superphosphate (50, 100 g/m²) in 5 replications.

Multiplication of azolla was highest (9 times original level) at the low inoculation level of 200 g/m² (Table 2). There was not much difference between the two superphosphate levels. Azolla at 200

g with 50 g superphosphate/m² seems to multiply well.

The maximum temperature range was 29-39° C. It also appears that azolla multiplies well at higher temperatures. ■

Effect of neem cake-blended urea on the yield of wetland rice

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Trials at University Research Centre, Aduthurai, during 1978-79 kharif assessed the merits of neem cake-coated urea and coal-tar-treated urea basally or split applied. The soil is clay loam with low nitrogen, medium phosphorus, and high potassium. Soil pH is 7.5. The rice variety tested was IR20.

The trials were laid in a randomized block design replicated four times. Urea was mixed with neem cake by 1) blending the cake with 30% by weight of urea in a plastic bag shaken vigorously, and 2) mixing the cake with 30% by weight

Effect of neem cake-blended urea on rice yields. Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	
	1978	1979
Control	2.2	4.9
Urea-blended neem cake @ 30% by weight, basal application	2.8	5.0
Urea-coated neem cake (30%) using coal tar and kerosene, basal application	2.6	5.1
Urea coated with coal tar and kerosene, basal application	2.7	5.2
Incorporation of neem cake in flooded soil, followed in a week by urea, basal application	3.1	5.6
Urea only, basal application	2.9	5.3
Urea split application (25% basal, 50% at active tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation)	3.4	5.9
Urea coated with coal tar and kerosene, split application (25% basal, 50% at active tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation)	3.6	6.0
SE	0.22	0.10
CD	0.50	0.29

of urea pretreated with a solution of coal tar and kerosene.

Split application of coal tar- and kerosene-coated urea recorded significantly higher grain yields than all treatments except split application of urea

alone (see table).

Treating urea with coal tar and kerosene and applying in split doses (25% basal, 50% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation) showed promise in increasing N use efficiency and grain yield. ■

Environment and its influence

Effects of laser seed treatment on rice panicle characteristics

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Four lasers (Table 1) were used in treating seeds of indica rice varieties.

Treating the variety Zhen-Zhu-Ai with He-Ne laser did not advance the date of heading (Table 2), but it increased primary rachis-branches by 13.4%, secondary rachis-branches by 11.4%, filled grains by 19.8%, and percentage of filled grains by 1.0%. The same treatment on Zhai-Ye-Qing increased the secondary rachis-branches by 13.7-38.3%, 1,000-grain weight by 6.5-11.8%, and filled grains by 4-6 grains/panicle (Table 3).

Seed treatment with Ai laser did not

Table 1. Wavelength and power density of 4 lasers. Guangzhou, China.

Laser	Wavelength	Power density ^a
CO ₂ laser	10.6 μ	20 w/cm ²
He-Ne laser	6328 Å	5 mw/cm ²
Ar ⁺ laser	4880, 5145 Å	5.7 w/cm ²
N ₂ laser	3771 Å	66-88 mw/cm ²

^aw = watts, mw = milliwatts.

Table 2. Effect of laser treatment on the heading date of rice. Guangzhou, China, 1980.

Treatment	Heading date	
	Zhen-Zhu-Ai	Zhai-Ye-Qing
Control	4 Jun	6 Jun
He-Ne laser	6 Jun	6 Jun
Ar ⁺ laser	4 Jun	8 Jun
N ₂ laser	5 Jun	6 Jun
Control	9 Jun	6 Jun
CO ₂ laser	6 Jun	9 Jun

advance panicle emergence but it increased secondary rachis-branches by

12.0% for Zhen-Zhu-Ai and by 6.6% for Zhai-Ye-Qing. The treatment also increased the percentage of filled grains by 5.0-8.8% and by 11.8% for the 2 varieties. The Ar⁺ laser was more effective for 20- to 30-minute treatments with Zhen-Zhu-Ai and for 3 minutes with Zhai-Ye-Qing.

Seed treatment with N₂ laser did not advance the heading stage of either Zhen-Zhu-Ai or Zhai-Ye-Qing, nor did it affect their dry seed status or germination rate. But it increased secondary rachis-branches of Zhen-Zhu-Ai seeds by about 32.0%, the number of grains per ear by about 12.2%, and the 1,000 grain weight about 5.5%. The N₂ laser treatment of seeds had the same effects on dry and germinating seeds of Zhai-Ye-Qing, except that it decreased the grain number per panicle. Hence, the

Table 3. Effect of laser treatments on panicle characteristics of rice. GuangZhou, China, 1980.

Treatment	Panicle characteristics ^a				
	Primary rachis-branches (no.)	Secondary rachis-branches (no.)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Fertile (%)	1,000 grain wt (g)
	<i>Zhen-Zhu-Ai</i>				
Control	9.7	14.1	88.0	88.8	23.7
He-Ne laser	11.0	15.9	107.8	89.8	23.6
Ar ⁺ laser	11.0	15.8	101.4	96.6	24.6
N ₂ laser	9.3	18.8	110.2	90.0	25.0
	<i>Zhai- Ye-Qing</i>				
Control	10.5	14.6	89.7	86.4	23.0
He-N laser	9.8	16.6	95.0	89.1	25.1
Ar ⁺ laser	10.0	15.5	102.0	91.5	25.1
N ₂ laser	9.0	15.0	18.8	88.1	25.4

^aMean of 20 panicles inspected. For the laser treatment, germinated seeds were planted in pots and placed in the field garden.

Table 4. Effect of CO₂-laser treatment on panicle characteristics of rice, Guangzhou, China, 1980.

Treatment	Panicle characteristic ^a				
	Primary rachis-branches (no.)	Secondary rachis-branches (no.)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Fertile (%)	1,000 grain wt (g)
	<i>Zhen-Zhu-Ai</i>				
Control	10.1	18.7	87.4	76.5	21.6
CO ₂ laser	12.1	18.4	124.4	91.8	23.7
	<i>Zhai- Ye-Qing</i>				
Control	8.8	15.6	70.2	12.1	21.6
CO ₂ laser	9.0	15.4	85.8	90.1	23.2

^aMean of 20 panicles inspected.

efficiency of the N₂ laser treatment differs with variety and with seed status.

CO₂ laser treatment of Zhen-Zhu-Ai increased its 1,000-grain weight about 19.0% and number of filled grains by 18.2-37.0 grains/panicle (Table 4). For Zhai-Ye-Qing, CO₂ laser treatment

increased the 1,000-grain weight by 5.5% and the number of filled grains by 15.5-15.8 grains/panicle, and delayed panicle emergence by 2-3 days.

Seed treatment with all four lasers slightly decreased the protein content of rough rice. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Evaluation of new technology developed at Walagambahuwa Minor Tank Settlement in Sri Lanka

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The Walagambahuwa settlement is typical of 10,000 similar settlements with 100-120,000 ha of wetland paddy in the dry zone of Sri Lanka. Lands below the

minor tanks have been cultivated to rice only once every 5 or 6 years. Settlers harvest a successful rice crop only if wet season rainfall exceeds 1,200 mm.

New technology developed at the site has two major components — timely cultivation with the onset of wet season rainfall and a rice variety that will mature in 3-3 1/2 months. This combination allows a successful rice crop every year and the collection in tanks of runoff that is used for an additional rice

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crop or other highland crops in the dry season.

This technology has increased the paddy production in the area by a factor of 3-3 1/2 the last 5 years.

Two similar tanks in the same agro-ecological area, with and without the new technology, were compared.

The second village, Mudaperumagama, is 10-15 miles away from Walagambahuwa. Socioeconomic conditions are similar to those of Walagambahuwa. Per capita income is low and each family has 4-5 members.

Rainfall in 1980-81 was just above average:

191.8 mm in September,
212.8 in October,
460.8 in November,
108.3 in December, and
68.8 in January.

Farmers at Walagambahuwa cultivated the whole paddy under the tank with no supplementary irrigation. Average yield was 2.9 t/ha. Forty-five percent of the farmers harvested more than 3 t/ha; 28% 2-3 t/ha; and 27% less than 2 t/ha.

The farmers also saved sufficient water in the tank to use during the dry season for another rice crop or highland crops.

Farmers at Mudaperumagama started traditional paddy cultivation in late December. The crop was seeded in late January. Land preparation for paddy was by puddling, using a lot of water from the tank. The crop was raised solely with water drawn from the tank. At heading time the crop experienced moisture stress because the tank had no water for further irrigation. Forty-seven percent of the farmers harvested 0.2 t/ha and 53% 0.6-1.1 t/ha.

With the tank completely dry, there was no hope for another cultivation during the dry season. ■